

WKB Versus Classical Density Approach to High Energy Level Entropy for an Oscillator

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We focus on two approaches (1), (2) presented in the literature for calculating the high energy Shannon's spatial entropy: $-\int dx W_n(x)W_n(x) \ln(W_n(x)W_n(x))$ where $W_n(x)$ is the high n quantum wavefunction for an oscillator potential $V(x) = \frac{1}{2}kx^2$. We examine how scaling can be used to find the leading n term in both cases, namely $\ln(n+0.5)$ ((1)).

In the first case, which is the simplest, one directly uses a classical density given by $Cdx/|v(x)|$, where $v(x) = \sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$. The bound problem is considered to exist between $-x_n$ and x_n and we show that scaling in the integral leads immediately to ((1)).

The WKB approach is a little more complicated, but also depends on scaling to obtain ((1)). In (2) a detailed calculator is presented to demonstrate the leading term ((1)) plus a second non- n term. Here, we only consider the leading order term in n and so only use the features (2):

$f(x) = \sqrt{2m(E - \frac{1}{2}kx^2)}$, We use $k=1$. $\phi(x) = \int_{x_n}^x f(t) dt$ and

$W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) / f(x)$

We demonstrate that $\cos()$ is an even function in $g(x) = \int_{x_n}^x f(t)dt$ for $x>0$ and so show that scaling is again the reason for ((1)).

For both approaches, we use: $E_n = \frac{1}{2}kx_n^2$ and $x_n = \{B(k)(n+0.5)\}^{1/(1+k)}$ taken from (2). We only consider $k=1$, i.e. the oscillator.

Classical Density Approach to Finding High Energy Level Entropy

Shannon's entropy is given by: $S = -\int_{-x_n}^{x_n} d(x) \ln(d(x))$ ((2))

Here $-x_n$ and x_n are classical turning points, which should be relevant if the energy level approaches infinite.

From (1), $d(x) = W_n(x)W_n(x) = C / \sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$ ((3)) with $V(x) = \frac{1}{2}kx^2$

Here $E_n = \frac{1}{2}kx_n^2$. First, we check the n dependence of the normalization constant C .

$C \int_{-x_n}^{x_n} dx \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m(E-V)}} = 1$ ((4))

Changing variables to $x \rightarrow x/x_n$ yields: $C x_n / x_n^{(k+1)} \int_{-1,1} dy \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m(1-y^2)}}$

This means that C goes as: $x_n^{-(k+1)} = (n+0.5)^{-\{(k+1)/(1+k)\}}$ ((5))

For $k=1$, C is n independent.

For $k=1$

$$S = - \int dx d(x) \ln(d(x)) = - (x^n/x^n) \int_{-1,1} dy d(y) \{ \ln(d(y) + \ln(x^n)) \}$$

This leads to a leading order of: Entropy proportional to $\ln(x^n) = \ln(n+0.5)$ ((6))

WKB Approach

The WKB approach given in (2) yields a first order $1/(1+k) \ln(n+0.5)$ term for entropy plus a k dependent second term. Here we are only concerned about the leading order n term. We only consider $k=1$.

We use the WKB wavefunction:

$$W_n(x) = C_n \cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) / f(x) \quad ((7)) \quad \text{where } f(x) = \sqrt{x^n \text{ power } 2k - x \text{ power } 2k}$$

Thus, $f(x)$ is even in x . $\phi(x) = \int (x, x^n) f(t) dt$

We first consider C_n , the normalization constant and its dependence on n :

$$1 = x^n \int_{-1,1} dy C_n C_n \cos(g(y) - \pi/4) \cos(g(y) - \pi/4) / \{ x^n \text{ power } k \sqrt{1 - y \text{ power } 2k} \} \quad ((8))$$

where $y=x/x^n$. Thus:

$$1 = C_n C_n B(k) x^n (\text{power } 1-k) \quad ((9)) \quad \text{For } k=1 \text{ which we use, } C_n \text{ has no } n \text{ dependence.}$$

One may then evaluate Shannon's entropy.

$$S = - \int_{-x^n, x^n} W_n(x) W_n(x) \ln(W_n W_n) \quad ((10))$$

To evaluate this integral we use scaling, i.e. $x \rightarrow x/x^n$.

Before performing this integral, we wish to show that:

$\cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4)$ is even in its argument and $\sin(\phi(x) - \pi/4)$ odd as this is important to the result.

We start with the definition: $\phi(x) = \int (x, x^n) f(t) dt$.

We first note that: for $x>0$ one has $\phi(x)$ and for $x<0$ Area - $\phi(x)$ where Area is given by:

$$\pi/2 \text{ is obtained by evaluating: } \text{Area} = \int_{-x^n, x^n} \sqrt{x^n \text{ power } 2k - x \text{ power } 2k} dx \quad ((11))$$

Changing variables to x/x_n one has:

$$\text{Area} = x_n^{\text{power}(k+1)} \int_{-1,1} \sqrt{1 - t^{\text{power}(2k)}} dt$$

For $k=1$, one has: $\text{Area} = x_n^{\text{power}(k+1)} \pi/2$ if one changes variables $t = \sin(\theta)$.

and uses $\int \cos(\theta) \cos(\theta) d\theta + \int \sin(\theta) \sin(\theta) d\theta = \int d\theta$.

$$\text{Area} = \pi/2 x_n x_n \quad ((12))$$

We wish to show that $\cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4)$ is even in $\phi(x)$ and $\sin(\phi(x) - \pi/4)$ odd.

In principle, we expect $\cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4)$ to be even because otherwise one would have a skewed wavefunction between $-x_n$ and x_n which is unphysical.

We first note that one may always use a ruler such that $x_n=1$. In such a case, $\text{Area} = \pi/2$ and one must consider:

$$\text{For } x>0: \cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) = \cos(\phi) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \sin(\phi) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$\text{For } x<0: \cos(\pi/2 - \phi(x) - \pi/4) = \cos(\phi) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sin(\phi)$$

For $\sin(\phi(x) - \pi/4)$ one has:

$$\text{For } x>0: \sin(\phi(x) - \pi/4) = -\cos(\phi) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \sin(\phi) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$\text{For } x<0: \sin(\pi/2 - \phi(x) - \pi/4) = \cos(\phi) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} - \sin(\phi) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Thus, one has the even-odd behaviour expected.

Next, we use these results to scale Shannon's entropy.

Given that C_n has no n dependence for $k=1$, one has:

$$S = - \int_{-x_n, x_n} dx \cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) \cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) / f(x) \ln\{\cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) \cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) / f(x)\}$$

The function: $\cos(\phi(x) - \pi/4) / f(x)$ is even in x and so the whole integrand is even because $f(x)$ is even in x .

One may change variables (scale) to x/x_n . This means that the bounds change to $(-1,1)$ and $dx \rightarrow (dx/x_n) x_n$. $f(x) = x_n \sqrt{1 - x^2/x_n^2}$.

This means that $1/f(x)$ in front of \ln yields a $1/x^n$ which cancels x^n from dx/x^n .
There is still a term: $\ln(1/x^n)$ which is important which comes from $f(x)$ in the $\ln\{\}$.

One may ask if the integrand is n dependent. To see it is, one may take d/dn of the integrand.
The function $f(x)$ is now $f(x/x^n)=f(y)$ and has no x^n because this has been dealt with above.
Thus, one only has n through x^n in $\cos(\phi(x)-\pi/4)$.

d/dn on \cos leaving $\ln\{\}$ along yields: $-\cos() \sin()$. As shown above, $\sin()$ is an odd function and so this term becomes 0 after integration.

d/dn on $\ln\{\}$ leaving $\cos()\cos()$ alone again yields $\cos()\sin()$ which is also odd. Thus, the only n dependence is through $\ln(x^n)$ which came from $1/f(x)$ in the argument of $\ln\{\}$.

Thus: $S = -\ln(x^n) = -\ln(n+.5)$ to leading order.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider two different approaches for finding Shannon's entropy in the high energy level limit for an oscillator. The first approach uses a classical density $d(x)=C/|v(x)|$ and scaling. The second approach uses a WKB wavefunction. We suggest that scaling also holds, but use even-odd function properties to show that only this piece of n dependence remains which again yields: $S = -\ln(n+.5)$.

References

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